

HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ACCESS-04-01

(Excellence Hubs)

“Excellence hub in green technologies: Introducing innovation ecosystems in the Mediterranean food value chain”

EXCEL4MED

Report on the Identification of Bottlenecks for Innovation Diffusion within Value Chains

Deliverable number: D2.2

Version 1.3

Project Acronym: EXCEL4MED

Project Full Title: Excellence hub in green technologies: Introducing innovation ecosystems in the Mediterranean food value chain

Call: HORIZON WIDERA 2023

Topic: HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ACCESS-04-01

Type of Action: HORIZON-CSA

Grant Number: 101087147

Project URL: <https://excel4med.eu/>

Editor:	Georgios Kleftodimos
Deliverable nature:	Report (R)
Dissemination level:	PUBLIC (PU)
Contractual Delivery Date:	31 December 2023
Actual Delivery Date:	29 December 2023
Number of pages:	57
Keywords:	Q methodology, stakeholders' perspectives, value chain, novel food technologies, sustainability
Authors:	Aybike Bayraktar, Zehra Basaran, Seyhan Sevde Cagiran, Teresa Latorre Carrascosa, Paolo Prospero, Georgios Kleftodimos
Peer review:	Natassa Kapetanakou - SEVT George Katsaros – ELGO Diana Miceli - TMC

Table of Contents

List of Figures.....	4
List of Tables	4
Abbreviations	5
Abstract	6
1. Introduction.....	7
2. Methodology	9
2.1 Definition of the methodology	9
2.2 Applied methodology for Task 2.2.....	10
3. Results of Q-methodology	12
3.1 Results of Q-methodology analysis in Malta	12
3.2 Results of Q-methodology analysis in Greece	30
3.3 Comparison the perspectives of stakeholders in Greece and Malta	50
4. Conclusions.....	53
References	54

List of Figures

Figure 1 WP2 and its tasks.....	8
Figure 2 Research methodology	11
Figure 3 Idealized Q-sort for Factor 1 in Malta.....	24
Figure 4 Idealized Q-sort for Factor 2 in Malta.....	25
Figure 5 Idealized Q-sort for Factor 3 in Malta.....	26
Figure 6 Idealized Q-sort for Factor 1 in Greece.....	44
Figure 7 Idealized Q-sort for Factor 2 in Greece.....	45
Figure 8 Idealized Q-sort for Factor 3 in Greece.....	46

List of Tables

Table 1 Composition of the P-set in Malta	12
Table 2 Factor matrix with an X indicating a defining sort in Malta	13
Table 3 Factor Q sort values for each statement in Malta	14
Table 4 Factor arrays by themes in Malta	18
Table 5 Factor 1 tops six most agree/most disagree statements in Malta.....	27
Table 6 Factor 2 tops six most agree/most disagree statements in Malta.....	28
Table 7 Factor 3 tops six most agree/most disagree statements in Malta.....	29
Table 8 Composition of the P-set in Greece	30
Table 9 Factor matrix with an X indicating a defining sort in Greece	31
Table 10 Factor Q sort values for each statement in Greece	33
Table 11 Factor arrays by themes in Greece	38
Table 12 Factor 1 tops six most agree/most disagree statements in Greece.....	47
Table 13 Factor 2 tops six most agree/most disagree statements in Greece.....	48
Table 14 Factor 3 tops six most agree/most disagree statements in Greece.....	49

Abbreviations

CIHEAM - Centre International de Hautes *É*tudes Agronomiques Méditerranéennes

IAMM - Institut Agronomique Méditerranéen de Montpellier

PCA - Principal component analysis

R&I - Research and innovation

TMC - The Malta Chamber

TRL - Technology Readiness Level

WP - Work package

Abstract

This report has been developed as part of the EXCEL4MED project. This report aims to identify the bottlenecks in the diffusion of innovation in value chains. For this purpose, a Q methodology study was conducted in Greece and Malta. The results of this report are expected to support the project partners in subsequent tasks and shed light on the path of those who want to research this subject in academia.

1. Introduction

The main objective of the EXCEL4MED project is to create an Excellence Hub in Mediterranean fruit supply chains. To achieve the primary goal of the EXCEL4MED project, seven specific goals were identified:

- To develop excellent and sustainable place-based process-innovation ecosystems in Malta and Greece that contribute to producing added-value food products and reduce waste along the food chain.
- To create joint R&I strategies in teaming and developing concrete action plans and standard investment plans for R&I in food processing.
- To create R&I pilot projects demonstrating food processing and valorization activities that reach a Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 7.
- To create new business opportunities, especially for SMEs in waste processing and the production of functional foods.
- To achieve improved knowledge transfer and development of entrepreneurial skills, while up-taking innovative green technologies in food processing valorization.
- To develop new competencies and skills for researchers, entrepreneurs, and professionals in R&I domains of food science and create poles of attraction for talents in Greece and Malta.
- To raise public and scientific awareness by providing effective dissemination and exploitation of project's outcomes through scientific events open to all parties/stakeholders, including industrial/commercial user groups.

WP2 and tasks

As part of the EXCEL4MED project, WP2 (leader TMC) is cross border joint R&I strategy aligned with strategic priorities aim to achieve these objectives:

- Establish a perceptual map of consumer behaviours, purchasing habits and food losses/waste.
- Identify bottlenecks for innovation diffusion within the value chains.
- Provide stakeholders with tailored and innovative Living Labs as a base of an interactive, participative and open Ecosystem of Innovation for improved organizational models and value chain governance.
- Identify limitations and opportunities of existing business models in the Mediterranean supply chains.

To achieve these objectives, four different tasks were identified (Figure 1). The first task is an assessment of the factors that are essential towards developing a market-oriented strategy. The second task is a meso-economic analysis of innovation's impacts and diffusion conditions within industrial chains and territories. The third task is innovation-oriented Living Labs (LLs).

Furthermore, the last task is to map stakeholders' organization models. As part of the WP2, CIHEAM-IAMM is the leader of the Task 2.2 “Meso-economic analysis of impacts and diffusion conditions of the innovation within industrial chains and territories”. This task aims to identify the nature of risks and uncertainties the stakeholders perceive towards novel techniques. For this task, we used Q-methodology to explore the potential capacity of the stakeholders to adapt to the technological change linked to innovative techniques.

Figure 1 WP2 and its tasks

2. Methodology

2.1 Definition of the methodology

The applied methodology for this task is Q methodology, which explores the potential capacity of the stakeholders to adapt to the technological change linked to innovative techniques. Q methodology was created in 1935 by psychologist William Stephenson, who thought it would be an alternative to traditional qualitative and quantitative empirical methods (van Exel & De Graaf, 2005; Brown, 1980; McKeown & Thomas, 1988). Q methodology is a methodology that uses both qualitative and quantitative methods for data collection and analysis. Q methodology is of great importance for research in social disciplines and offers a scientific method for examining subjectivity while preserving the depth, diversity, and uniqueness of a more humanistic approach (Brown, 1980; Eden et al., 2005). According to Brown et al., 2008: 'Q-methodology is best understood as a type of research that identifies the operant subjectivity of individuals concerning a particular subject. The methodology encompasses a broader philosophy of how subjectivity can best be studied, an inherent epistemology and a method that includes a series of well-defined steps or phases'. According to Millar et al. 2022, 'Q methodology is a set of related techniques designed to examine 'subjectivity' (opinions, opinions, beliefs, values, tastes)'. Although it was initially used for social sciences, the areas in which Q methodology is used have expanded over time and started to be used in many different disciplines, such as medicine and health fields (McParland et al., 2011; Chinnis et al., 2001; Risdon et al., 2003; Baker et al., 2006), agricultural sciences (Bumbudsanpharoke et al., 2009; Zagata, 2010; Lehrer & Sneegas, 2018), environmental sciences (Frantzi et al., 2009; Hermelingmeier & Nicholas, 2017; Amaruzaman et al., 2017), and policy (Durning & Osuna, 1994; Gen & Wright, 2018).

Q methodology primarily deals with human subjectivity and highlights qualitatively, but in the data collection and analysis phase, it emphasizes quantitatively using correlation and factor analysis (Watts & Stenner, 2007). Q methodology has six stages: (i) definition of concourse, (ii) development of a Q-set, (iii) selection of participants called P-set, (iv) conducting Q-sorting, (v) analysis phase with correlation and factor analysis, and finally (vi) interpretation (Ramlo & Newman, 2011; Jeffares & Skelcher, 2011). The first step in the Q study begins with creating a series of statements about the topic under investigation, called a concourse (Davies et al., 2005). This stage involves an in-depth literature review and is the stage where explanations about possible situations that people have made or could do regarding the subject are collected and brought together. In the second stage, a Q set is prepared by selecting the best expressions representing the subject (Watts & Stenner, 2012). This stage involves selecting final state expressions by reducing the expressions selected from the concourse determined in the previous stage. The third stage is the selection stage of the stakeholders, called the P-set, that is, the participants who will participate in the Q study (Nijnik et al., 2009). In the fourth stage, called conducting Q-sorting, participants are asked to rank the statements they agree with least, are neutral, and agree with the most. The Q-sorting phase can be carried out face-to-face or remotely, depending on the purpose of the study. In the sixth stage, analysis, correlation and factor analysis are carried out, and the last stage includes the interpretation of the results (Webler et al., 2003).

2.2 Applied methodology for Task 2.2

The research methodology applied for Task 2.2 is given in Figure 2. For the first step of the Q study, an extensive literature review examined stakeholders' opinions on adopting novel food process technologies. Following the literature review, 250 statements on the subject were extracted initially. The statements were divided into four categories to represent all perceptions: social, economic, environmental and governance. Later, a workshop was held at CIHEAM-IAMM with seven stakeholders in February 2023 to prepare a Q set. After this workshop, 40 statements (10 statements for social, 10 for economic, 9 for environmental and 11 for governance) were selected as final, taking into account the opinions of the stakeholders, and the Q set was given its final form. In the third stage, the potential stakeholders who will participate in the Q study were selected in cooperation with the project partners in Malta and Greece, which are the case studies of the study. Thus, the participants called P-set were determined. Participants were selected based on their suitability for the study. Stakeholders selected included scientists, the food industry, farmers and farmers' organisations, policymakers and consumers.

Q-sorting was conducted face-to-face in Malta at the Maltese Living Lab in May 2023 and Greece at the Greek Living Lab in July. While twenty-four well-informed stakeholders attended the Q method workshop in Malta, twenty-seven well-informed stakeholders participated in the workshop in Greece. Stakeholders were asked to rank the 40 statements given to them according to how much they agreed or disagreed on a table ranging from -4 strongly disagree to +4 strongly agree. In addition, the participants were asked to fill out the table containing socio-demographic characteristics such as age, profession and gender on the papers given to them and to write their thoughts at the end of the study. In this way, a set of ranked data was collected for each participant, representing individual perceptions and socio-demographics. The analysis was conducted separately for both countries, and PQMethod software version 2.35 was used for statistical analysis. The analysis results are interpreted below for both countries separately, and the statements are compared.

Figure 2 Research methodology

3. Results of Q-methodology

3.1 Results of Q-methodology analysis in Malta

First Q methodology workshop was held with 24 stakeholders at the Maltese Living Lab on May 4, 2023, in Malta. This workshop aimed to explore the thoughts and perspectives of different stakeholder groups with different characteristics on adopting novel food process technologies in Malta.

Table 1, called P-set, in which the participants' information is included in the Q methodology, is given below. According to the composition of the P set, Factor 1 represents one farmer, five research/governmental organizations, one consumer, and one food industry. Factor 2 represents two industries, two consumers, and five research/governmental organizations. Factor 3 represents two industries, one consumer, one farmer, and three research/governmental organizations. The 24 Q-sorts were entered into the PQ Method software for data analysis. All the Q-sorts loaded significantly in the factors used to constitute three factors.

This case study used principal component analysis (PCA) and varimax rotation for factor analysis. The PCA allowed the specificity of each type and their commonalities to be considered. Therefore, stakeholders with similar opinions were grouped into one factor. Specifically, they explained the following factor loadings, or correlations between the interviews: the first factor (F1) accounted for 14% of the variance and is associated with eight stakeholders; the second factor (F2) accounted for 14% of the variance and is associated with nine stakeholders; the third factor (F3) accounted for the 10% of the variance and is associated with seven stakeholders. All the factors are associated with a factor group (Table 1). We identified three different viewpoints of the participants about the elements that would facilitate participants' adoption of the novel food process technologies. The selected three-factor solution accounted for 24 out of the 24 participants (all samples) and explained 38% of the total variance.

Table 1 Composition of the P-set in Malta

No	Gender	Age	Type of stakeholder	Factors		
				1	2	3
1	M	46	Research/governmental organization		Factor 2	
2	M	62	Consumer representative/ consumer	Factor 1		
3	M	35	Industry			Factor 3
4	F	38	Research/governmental organization	Factor 1		
5	F	43	Consumer association/consumer		Factor 2	
6	F	39	Research/governmental organization			Factor 3
7	F	21	Consumer			Factor 3
8	M	43	Industry		Factor 2	
9	F	23	Research/governmental organization	Factor 1		
10	M	51	Research/governmental organization		Factor 2	

11	F	39	Research/governmental organization	Factor 1		
12	F	46	Research/governmental organization		Factor 2	
13	M	49	Industry	Factor 1		
14	M	30	Research/governmental organization			Factor 3
15	F	21	Research/governmental organization	Factor 1		
16	M	53	Farmer			Factor 3
17	M	37	Consumer		Factor 2	
18	F	31	Research/governmental organization			Factor 3
19	F	25	Research/governmental organization		Factor 2	
20	M	63	Farmer	Factor 1		
21	M	34	Research/governmental organization		Factor 2	
22	M	30	Research/governmental organization	Factor 1		
23	M	26	Industry		Factor 2	
24	M	37	Industry			Factor 3

Table 2 shows the factor loading per each Q-sort and asterisks and different colours indicate a defining sort for the corresponding factor. Factor 1 and Factor 2 explain 14% of the total variance, and Factor 3 explains 10%. All factors together explain 38% of the total variance.

Table 2 Factor matrix with an X indicating a defining sort in Malta

Q sort	Participant code	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3
1	050401	-0.1879	0.7663*	-0.0879
2	050402	0.4979*	0.0732	0.0517
3	050403	0.2777	0.1050	0.5347*
4	050404	0.6651*	-0.1490	-0.4245
5	050405	0.2466	0.5627*	0.2059
6	050407	0.2763	0.0410	0.3440*
7	050408	0.2101	-0.2390	0.4197*
8	050409	0.0498	0.3719*	-0.2887
9	050410	0.5543*	0.0962	0.0272
10	050411	0.2560	0.5111*	-0.2691
11	050412	0.5431*	0.0495	0.0011
12	050413	-0.0700	0.5977*	-0.2186
13	050414	0.6746*	-0.0084	0.0094
14	050415	0.4801	-0.0501	-0.5440*

15	050416	0.7070*	0.3515	0.0926
16	050417	-0.0460	0.0271	0.5391*
17	050418	0.3158	0.4677*	-0.2305
18	050419	0.2467	-0.0114	-0.3910*
19	050420	0.1765	0.4978*	0.2963
20	050421	0.3984*	-0.0901	0.1228
21	050422	0.0972	0.6320*	0.0082
22	050423	0.5045*	0.2383	-0.0029
23	050424	-0.0408	0.6636*	0.2465
24	050425	0.0659	-0.1634	0.6099*
% Expl. Var.		14	14	10

Table 3 shows factor Q sort values for each statement in Malta. The factor arrays indicate the level of agreement or disagreement of each factor with each statement used for the Q-sort. The range is from -4 (strongly disagree) to 4 (strongly agree). Table 3 also shows significance levels of statements. According to Table 3, except for statements 15 and 24, all statements were found to be significant at the 1% and 5% levels.

Significant values for each factor are shown with a different colour, and expressions with an asterisk beside them indicate significance at the 1% level. If there is an asterisk in the 'significance level' line, the status expression is significant at the 1% level for all factors. Statements 4, 7, 20, 21, 22, 28, 30, 31, 32, and 34 were significant at all significance levels and for all factors ($p < 0.01$ and $p < 0.05$).

Table 3 Factor Q sort values for each statement in Malta

No	Statements	Factor Arrays			Significance level
		1	2	3	
1	Novel food process technologies can raise awareness and interest in local communities on the potential of local and traditional products that are processed through these new technologies.	1	0	4*	
2	Novel food process technologies can improve the quality of consumer lives, offering tastier and healthier products while enhancing the working conditions of processors.	0	-1	-2*	
3	Novel food process technologies promote and connect the importance of sustainability to general culture.	1	-1	-1	
4	Novel food process technologies offer a better - and novel - juice product by reducing the sugars while maintaining their natural profile of vitamins, minerals and fibres.	3*	1*	-2*	*
5	Novel food process technologies can improve the skills development of employees.	0*	-3	-3	

6	Novel food process technologies improve the awareness of the sustainability of workers in the value chains, consumers and stakeholders.	0*	-1	-2	
7	Novel food process technologies might put aside traditional processing practices and reduce workforce needs.	3*	-4*	0*	*
8	Novel food process technologies can improve the quality of life of workers in the food industry and the personal development of workers, producers and stakeholders concerning sustainability.	0*	-3	-2	
9	Citrus/pomegranate growing protects and preserves rural territories' historical and cultural values.	-1	-2*	0	
10	Novel food products using green technologies can help people have a balanced diet.	3*	1	0	
11	Novel food process technologies will increase opportunities for partnership with different stakeholders of value chains.	2	1*	2	
12	Novel food process technologies will further diversify production activities and practices.	4	1*	3	
13	I believe novel food process technologies allow for more environment-friendly and cost-effective production.	2*	0	-1	
14	Novel food process technologies and practices must be communicated appropriately to targeted customers, in order to transfer knowledge and awareness to purchasers and consumers about their innovative value and potential for green production.	4	4	0*	
15	Novel food process technologies allow for increasing and better targeting of environmentally-friendly customers with economically accessible products.	0	0	0	
16	For applying novel food process technologies, it is necessary to have a supply of sustainable/environmentally-friendly resources (such as organic raw materials and environmentally sustainable resource supply).	0*	-2	-1	
17	Food products obtained from novel food process technologies will need appropriate distribution channels such as supermarkets, wholesalers, etc.	0	-1	1	
18	I think the cost of novel food process technologies should be lower than traditional technologies as the energy use should decrease.	1	-4*	0	
19	Producer revenues will increase as the sale price of novel food products will be relatively higher than those ones obtained from traditional technologies, especially with respect to costs.	-3	-3	1*	

20	Thanks to the novel food process technologies, small farmers can find the opportunity to market their citrus products and generate additional income.	0*	-2*	3*	*
21	Novel food process technologies should be used through efficient and sustainable sourcing of energy and water.	2*	4*	-1*	*
22	The use of novel food process technology for the production of the primary output produce should require efficient use of energy, water and materials.	2*	3*	-4*	*
23	Novel food process technologies help the efficient use of energy, water and materials in the production phase and waste reduction and efficient practices in the consumption phase.	1	2	-1*	
24	Novel food process technologies allow the spread and trigger of other production and consumption practices that avoid waste and encourage the reuse of technology and materials.	2	2	1	
25	Consumers using food products obtained from novel food process technologies are more aware of the environmental impact of their consumption patterns and apply environmentally-friendly and circular behaviours.	-1	-1	2*	
26	The use of novel food process technologies should involve the use of materials obtained from sustainable supply chains.	-1*	2	2	
27	I believe using of novel food process technologies should involve the choice of environmentally-friendly distribution channels for the related output products, such as trains, e-bikes, etc.	-4	0*	-2	
28	The use of novel food process technologies has a positive impact on the environment since it involves the consumption of processed products.	-4*	-1*	3*	*
29	Using novel food process technologies can bring environmental benefits in producing juices and smoothies because they reduce waste products and energy consumption.	1	0	2	
30	Novel food process technologies can be a tool for improving good governance and coordination among value chain stakeholders that are engaged in more sustainable food systems.	-2*	2*	-3*	*
31	Novel food process technologies adoption should be accompanied by consideration for not excluding less empowered stakeholders within the innovation value chain.	1*	3*	-3*	*
32	Novel food process technologies adoption can contribute to engagement in more ethical value chains.	-3*	3*	1*	*

33	Novel food process technologies adoption can contribute to overall complex sustainability strategies within the value chain.	-1*	2	1	
34	Novel food process technologies can provide protocols to regulate rules and standards for processors and stakeholders in the value chains.	-2*	0*	4*	*
35	Novel food process technologies can improve traceability and measurement systems across the processing dynamics (including the traceability of different processes of stakeholders).	-2*	1	1	
36	Novel food process technologies can improve the transparency of the flow of information through innovative and digital processes and practices.	-2	-2	0*	
37	Adopting novel food process technologies involve costs and risks regarding low coordination, adaptation of the new technology for producers and consumers (acceptability), excessive bureaucracy, exclusion and power imbalances.	-2*	0	-1	
38	Adopting novel food process technologies can benefit coordination, collaboration and transparency with other stakeholders engaged in the value chain.	-3*	0	0	
39	It is possible to encounter bureaucratic obstacles in adopting novel food process technologies.	-1	1	-4*	
40	Adopting novel food process technologies can result in high transaction and production costs.	-1	-2	2*	

According to Table 4, factor arrays are divided into themes which underpin the novel food process technologies. The darker green colour illustrates a more substantial degree of agreement, the darker grey colour a more robust disagreement and the yellow colour a neutral. According to this, it is clear that factors have different interests for different statements. For example, within the theme of social, it has been observed that while Factor 3 shows a high interest that novel food process technologies can raise awareness and interest in local communities about the potential of local and traditional products, Factor 2 does not show much interest in this (S: 1). Within the theme of economics, it is a positive result that all factors think that novel food process technologies will increase opportunities for partnership with different stakeholders of value chains (S: 11). All the factors agree on novel food process technologies will further diversify production activities and practices (S: 12). All the factors do not have a specific opinion on novel food process technologies allow for increasing and better targeting of environmentally-friendly customers with economically accessible products (S: 15). Within the theme of environmental, Factor 1 and Factor 2 think that novel food process technologies should be used through efficient and sustainable sourcing of energy and water, on the contrary, Factor 3 doesn't agree to this idea (S: 21). Within the governance theme, Factor 1 and Factor 2 think that adopting novel food process technologies cannot result in high transaction and production costs; since both factors include a high presence of research and governmental organizations, they provide us with an important clue (S: 40).

Table 4 Factor arrays by themes in Malta

Theme	No	Statements	Factor Arrays		
			1	2	3
Social	1	Novel food process technologies can raise awareness and interest in local communities on the potential of local and traditional products that are processed through these new technologies.	1	0	4
	2	Novel food process technologies can improve the quality of consumer lives, offering tastier and healthier products while enhancing the working conditions of processors.	0	-1	-2
	3	Novel food process technologies promote and connect the importance of sustainability to general culture.	1	-1	-1
	4	Novel food process technologies offer a better - and novel - juice product by reducing the sugars while maintaining their natural profile of vitamins, minerals and fibres.	3	1	-2
	5	Novel food process technologies can improve the skills development of employees.	0	-3	-3
	6	Novel food process technologies improve the awareness of the sustainability of workers in the value chains, consumers and stakeholders.	0	-1	-2
	7	Novel food process technologies might put aside traditional processing practices and reduce workforce needs.	3	-4	0
	8	Novel food process technologies can improve the quality of life of workers in the food industry and the personal development of workers, producers and stakeholders concerning sustainability.	0	-3	-2
	9	Citrus/pomegranate growing protects and preserves rural territories' historical and cultural values.	-1	-2	0
	10	Novel food products using green technologies can help people have a balanced diet.	3	1	0
Economic	11	Novel food process technologies will increase opportunities for partnership with different stakeholders of value chains.	2	1	2
	12	Novel food process technologies will further diversify production activities and practices.	4	1	3
	13	I believe novel food process technologies allow for more environment-friendly and cost-effective production.	2	0	-1

	14	Novel food process technologies and practices must be communicated appropriately to targeted customers, in order to transfer knowledge and awareness to purchasers and consumers about their innovative value and potential for green production.	4	4	0
	15	Novel food process technologies allow for increasing and better targeting of environmentally-friendly customers with economically accessible products.	0	0	0
	16	For applying novel food process technologies, it is necessary to have a supply of sustainable/environmentally-friendly resources (such as organic raw materials and environmentally sustainable resource supply).	0	-2	-1
	17	Food products obtained from novel food process technologies will need appropriate distribution channels such as supermarkets, wholesalers, etc.	0	-1	1
	18	I think the cost of novel food process technologies should be lower than traditional technologies as the energy use should decrease.	1	-4	0
	19	Producer revenues will increase as the sale price of novel food products will be relatively higher than those ones obtained from traditional technologies, especially with respect to costs.	-3	-3	1
	20	Thanks to the novel food process technologies, small farmers can find the opportunity to market their citrus products and generate additional income.	0	-2	3
Environmental	21	Novel food process technologies should be used through efficient and sustainable sourcing of energy and water.	2	4	-1
	22	The use of novel food process technology for the production of the primary output produce should require efficient use of energy, water and materials.	2	3	-4
	23	Novel food process technologies help the efficient use of energy, water and materials in the production phase and waste reduction and efficient practices in the consumption phase.	1	2	-1
	24	Novel food process technologies allow the spread and trigger of other production and consumption practices that avoid waste and encourage the reuse of technology and materials.	2	2	1
	25	Consumers using food products obtained from novel food process technologies are more aware of the environmental impact of their consumption patterns and apply environmentally-friendly and circular behaviours.	-1	-1	2

	26	The use of novel food process technologies should involve the use of materials obtained from sustainable supply chains.	-1	2	2
	27	I believe using of novel food process technologies should involve the choice of environmentally-friendly distribution channels for the related output products, such as trains, e-bikes, etc.	-4	0	-2
	28	The use of novel food process technologies has a positive impact on the environment since it involves the consumption of processed products.	-4	-1	3
	29	Using novel food process technologies can bring environmental benefits in producing juices and smoothies because they reduce waste products and energy consumption.	1	0	2
Governance	30	Novel food process technologies can be a tool for improving good governance and coordination among value chain stakeholders that are engaged in more sustainable food systems.	-2	2	-3
	31	Novel food process technologies adoption should be accompanied by consideration for not excluding less empowered stakeholders within the innovation value chain.	1	3	-3
	32	Novel food process technologies adoption can contribute to engagement in more ethical value chains.	-3	3	1
	33	Novel food process technologies adoption can contribute to overall complex sustainability strategies within the value chain.	-1	2	1
	34	Novel food process technologies can provide protocols to regulate rules and standards for processors and stakeholders in the value chains.	-2	0	4
	35	Novel food process technologies can improve traceability and measurement systems across the processing dynamics (including the traceability of different processes of stakeholders).	-2	1	1
	36	Novel food process technologies can improve the transparency of the flow of information through innovative and digital processes and practices.	-2	-2	0
	37	Adopting novel food process technologies involve costs and risks regarding low coordination, adaptation of the new technology for producers and consumers (acceptability), excessive bureaucracy, exclusion and power imbalances.	-2	0	-1

	38	Adopting novel food process technologies can benefit coordination, collaboration and transparency with other stakeholders engaged in the value chain.	-3	0	0
	39	It is possible to encounter bureaucratic obstacles in adopting novel food process technologies.	-1	1	-4
	40	Adopting novel food process technologies can result in high transaction and production costs.	-1	-2	2

Perspectives in Malta

There is no specific stakeholder typology with each factor; however, it is noted that representatives of governmental organizations and farmers emphasized the environmental and economic importance of novel food process technologies. The food industries demonstrated more interest, primarily social and concerning economic (Figures 3, 4, and 5).

Perspective 1

Factor 1 explains 14% of the study variance, and the eigenvalue is 5.600. Eight participants are significantly associated with this factor. Factor 1: 1 consumer, five research/governmental organizations, one food industry, and one farmer.

Factor 1 has been associated with economic and social benefits. Factor 1 believes that novel food process technologies will further diversify production activities and practices (S12: +4) and allow for more environment-friendly and cost-effective production (S13: +2). However, Factor 1 does not believe producer revenues will increase as the sale price of novel food products will be relatively higher than those obtained from traditional technologies, especially concerning costs (S19: -3). Factor 1 does not believe that using novel food process technologies positively impacts the environment (S28: -4). Additionally, they do not think new food processing technologies should include selecting environmentally friendly distribution channels for the relevant output products (S27: -4). This factor makes one think that novel food products using green technologies can help people have a balanced diet (S10: +3) and offer a better - and novel - juice product by reducing the sugars while maintaining their natural profile of vitamins, minerals, and fibres (S4: +3).

Perspective 2

Factor 2 explains 14% of the study variance, and the eigenvalue is 5.600. Nine participants are significantly associated with this factor. Factor 2: 5 research/governmental organizations, two consumers, two industries.

Factor 2 has been associated with governance procedures and environmental benefits. Factor 2 thinks that adopting novel food process technologies should consider and include stakeholders with less authority in the innovation value chain (S31: +3). Adopting novel food process technologies is important as it can further contribute to participation in ethical value chains and to overall complex sustainability strategies within the value chain (S32: +3, S33: +2). This group considers that novel food process technologies can be a tool to improve good governance and coordination among value chain stakeholders interested in more sustainable food systems (S30: +2). The environmental benefits of novel food process technologies are also important for this group. They mainly give the importance of efficient use of energy, water, and materials (S21: +4, S22: +3) and the reduction of waste (S24: +2, S23: +2).

They do not believe in the economic benefits of the novel food process technologies. For example, they do not think cost of novel food process technologies should be lower than traditional technologies as the energy use should decrease (S18: -4) or producer revenues will increase as the sale price of novel food products will be relatively higher than those obtained from traditional technologies, especially concerning costs (S19: -3) and thanks to the novel food process technologies, small farmers can find the opportunity to market their citrus products and generate additional income (S20: -2).

Perspective 3

Factor 3 explains 10% of the study variance, and the eigenvalue is 4.000. Ten participants are significantly associated with this factor. Factor 3 represents two industries, one consumer, one farmer and three research/governmental organizations.

Factor 3 emphasizes novel food process technologies' environmental, economic, and governance aspects. This group believes that novel food process technologies can provide protocols that set rules and standards for processors and stakeholders in value chains (S34: +4) and can raise awareness and interest in local communities on the potential of local and traditional products processed through these new technologies (S1: +4). Factor 3 believes that thanks to novel food processing technologies, small farmers can find the opportunity to market their citrus products and generate additional income (S20: +3). In addition, stakeholders in this factor think that novel food process technologies will further diversify production activities and practices (S12: +3).

Factor 3 thinks that new food technologies will also have a positive impact on the environment (S28: +3), and consumers using food products obtained from novel food process technologies are more aware of the environmental impact of their consumption patterns and apply environmentally friendly and circular behaviours (S25: +2).

Figure 3 Idealized Q-sort for Factor 1 in Malta

Strongly disagree

Strongly agree

-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3	4
27. I believe using of novel food process technologies ...	38. Adopting novel food process technologies ...	30. Novel food process technologies can be a tool for improving...	25. Consumers using food products obtained from ...	20. Thanks to the novel food process technologies, small ...	1. Novel food process technologies can raise awareness ...	21. Novel food process technologies should be used ...	4. Novel food process technologies offer a better - and novel...	14. Novel food process technologies and practices must be ...
28. The use of novel food process technologies has ...	19. Producer revenues will increase as the ...	37. Adopting novel food process technologies involve ...	9. Citrus/ pomegranate growing protects ...	6. Novel food process technologies improve the awareness of ...	31. Novel food process technologies adoption ...	13. I believe novel food process technologies allow ...	7. Novel food process technologies might put aside ...	12. Novel food process technologies will further diversify ...
	32. Novel food process technologies ...	34. Novel food process technologies can provide protocols to.	26. The use of novel food process technologies ...	5. Novel food process technologies can improve the skills ...	23. Novel food process technologies help the efficient ...	11. Novel food process technologies will increase ...	10. Novel food products using green technologies can ...	
		35. Novel food process technologies can improve traceability ...	39. It is possible to encounter bureaucratic ...	15. Novel food process technologies allow for increasing and better...	3. Novel food process technologies promote and ...	22. The use of novel food process technology for the ...		
		36. Novel food process technologies can improve the ...	40. Adopting novel food process technologies can ...	8. Novel food process technologies can improve the quality of ...	29. Using novel food process technologies can bring ...	24. Novel food process technologies allow the spread ...		
			33. Novel food process technologies ...	17. Food products obtained from novel food process ...	18. I think the cost of novel food process technologies ...			
				2. Novel food process technologies can improve the quality of...				
				16. For applying novel food process technologies, it is necessary to have...				

Figure 4 Idealized Q-sort for Factor 2 in Malta

Strongly disagree

Strongly agree

-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3	4
18. I think the cost of novel food process technologies...	8. Novel food process technologies can improve the ...	16. For applying novel food process technologies, it is...	3. Novel food process technologies promote and ...	38. Adopting novel food process technologies can benefit coordination...	11. Novel food process technologies will increase ...	24. Novel food process technologies allow the spread and...	22. The use of novel food process technology for the...	21. Novel food process technologies should be used through efficient...
7. Novel food process technologies might put aside ...	19. Producer revenues will increase as the sale price of novel...	20. Thanks to the novel food process technologies, small...	28. The use of novel food process technologies has ...	27. I believe using of novel food process technologies should ...	12. Novel food process technologies will further diversify...	26. The use of novel food process technologies should ...	32. Novel food process technologies adoption can ...	14. Novel food process technologies and practices must be ...
	5. Novel food process technologies can improve ...	40. Adopting novel food process technologies can...	25. Consumers using food products obtained from ...	15. Novel food process technologies allow for increasing and better...	39. It is possible to encounter bureaucratic ...	23. Novel food process technologies help the efficient ...	31. Novel food process technologies adoption should ...	
		36. Novel food process technologies can improve ...	2. Novel food process technologies can improve ...	1. Novel food process technologies can raise awareness and ...	4. Novel food process technologies offer a better - and novel...	30. Novel food process technologies can be a tool for ...		
		9. Citrus/ pomegranate growing protects ...	17. Food products obtained from novel food process ...	34. Novel food process technologies can provide protocols to regulate...	35. Novel food process technologies can improve ...	33. Novel food process technologies adoption can ...		
			6. Novel food process technologies improve ...	37. Adopting novel food process technologies involve costs and risks...	10. Novel food products using green technologies can ...			
				13. I believe novel food process technologies allow ...				
				29. Using novel food process technologies can bring environmental...				

Figure 5 Idealized Q-sort for Factor 3 in Malta

Strongly disagree

Strongly agree

-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3	4
22. The use of novel food process technology for the ...	5. Novel food process technologies can ...	4. Novel food process technologies offer a better - and novel - ...	13. I believe novel food process technologies allow ...	38. Adopting novel food process technologies can benefit coordination...	33. Novel food process technologies adoption can ...	40. Adopting novel food process technologies can ...	20. Thanks to the novel food process technologies, small ...	34. Novel food process technologies can provide protocols to...
39. It is possible to encounter bureaucratic ...	30. Novel food process technologies can...	2. Novel food process technologies can improve the quality ...	21. Novel food process technologies should be ...	14. Novel food process technologies and practices must be...	35. Novel food process technologies can improve ...	26. The use of novel food process technologies should ...	12. Novel food process technologies will further diversify...	1. Novel food process technologies can raise awareness and ...
	31. Novel food process technologies ...	8. Novel food process technologies can improve the quality ...	37. Adopting novel food process technologies ...	36. Novel food process technologies can improve the ...	24. Novel food process technologies allow the spread...	11. Novel food process technologies will increase...	28. The use of novel food process technologies has ...	
		6. Novel food process technologies improve the awareness of ...	3. Novel food process technologies promote ...	15. Novel food process technologies allow for increasing and better...	19. Producer revenues will increase as the sale price of novel ...	29. Using novel food process technologies can bring ...		
		27. I believe using of novel food process technologies should ...	23. Novel food process technologies help the efficient...	10. Novel food products using green technologies can help people have ...	17. Food products obtained from novel food process ...	25. Consumers using food products obtained from ...		
			16. For applying novel food process technologies, it is ...	9. Citrus/ pomegranate growing protects and preserves rural ...	32. Novel food process technologies adoption ...			
				7. Novel food process technologies might put aside traditional...				
				18. I think the cost of novel food process technologies ...				

Table 5 contains the top six most-agree and most disagree statements from Factor 1 stakeholders' viewpoint. The statements that Factor 1 attaches the most importance to, respectively, are the statements that they think will provide economic and social benefits of novel food process technologies. It was determined that the statements that Factor 1 gave the least importance to, were some governance and environmental statements.

Table 5 Factor 1 tops six most agree/most disagree statements in Malta

No	Statement	Z-score	Rank score
14	Novel food process technologies and practices must be communicated appropriately to targeted customers, in order to transfer knowledge and awareness to purchasers and consumers about their innovative value and potential for green production.	2.146	4
12	Novel food process technologies will further diversify production activities and practices.	1.631	4
4	Novel food process technologies offer a better - and novel - juice product by reducing the sugars while maintaining their natural profile of vitamins, minerals and fibres.	1.599	3
7	Novel food process technologies might put aside traditional processing practices and reduce workforce needs.	1.419	3
10	Novel food products using green technologies can help people have a balanced diet.	1.050	3
21	Novel food process technologies should be used through efficient and sustainable sourcing of energy and water.	1.033	2
36	Novel food process technologies can improve the transparency of the flow of information through innovative and digital processes and practices.	-1.317	-2
38	Adopting novel food process technologies can benefit coordination, collaboration and transparency with other stakeholders engaged in the value chain.	-1.372	-3
19	Producer revenues will increase as the sale price of novel food products will be relatively higher than those ones obtained from traditional technologies, especially with respect to costs.	-1.405	-3
32	Novel food process technologies adoption can contribute to engagement in more ethical value chains.	-1.458	-3
27	I believe using of novel food process technologies should involve the choice of environmentally-friendly distribution channels for the related output products, such as trains, e-bikes, etc.	-1.657	-4
28	The use of novel food process technologies has a positive impact on the environment since it involves the consumption of processed products.	-2.065	-4

Table 6 contains the top six most-agree and most disagree statements from Factor 2 stakeholders' viewpoint. The statements that Factor 2 attaches the most importance to, respectively, are the statements that they think will provide environmental benefits of novel food process technologies. It was determined that the statements that Factor 2 gave the least importance to, were some social benefits.

Table 6 Factor 2 tops six most agree/most disagree statements in Malta

No	Statement	Z-score	Grid position
21	Novel food process technologies should be used through efficient and sustainable sourcing of energy and water.	2.467	4
14	Novel food process technologies and practices must be communicated appropriately to targeted customers, in order to transfer knowledge and awareness to purchasers and consumers about their innovative value and potential for green production.	2.371	4
22	The use of novel food process technology for the production of the primary output produce should require efficient use of energy, water and materials.	1.790	3
32	Novel food process technologies adoption can contribute to engagement in more ethical value chains.	1.199	3
31	Novel food process technologies adoption should be accompanied by consideration for not excluding less empowered stakeholders within the innovation value chain.	1.172	3
24	Novel food process technologies allow the spread and trigger of other production and consumption practices that avoid waste and encourage the reuse of technology and materials.	0.797	2
9	Citrus/pomegranate growing protects and preserves rural territories' historical and cultural values.	-0.892	-2
8	Novel food process technologies can improve the quality of life of workers in the food industry and the personal development of workers, producers and stakeholders concerning sustainability.	-1.177	-3
19	Producer revenues will increase as the sale price of novel food products will be relatively higher than those ones obtained from traditional technologies, especially with respect to costs.	-1.316	-3
5	Novel food process technologies can improve the skills development of employees.	-1.356	-3
18	I think the cost of novel food process technologies should be lower than traditional technologies as the energy use should decrease.	-1.765	-4
7	Novel food process technologies might put aside traditional processing practices and reduce workforce needs.	-2.637	-4

Table 7 contains the top six most-agree and most disagree statements from Factor 3 stakeholders' viewpoint. The statements that Factor 3 attaches the most importance to, respectively, are the statements that they think will provide economic benefits of novel food process technologies. It was determined that the statements that Factor 3 gave the least importance to, were some governance and environmental statements.

Table 7 Factor 3 tops six most agree/most disagree statements in Malta

No	Statement	Z-score	Grid position
34	Novel food process technologies can provide protocols to regulate rules and standards for processors and stakeholders in the value chains.	1.654	4
1	Novel food process technologies can raise awareness and interest in local communities on the potential of local and traditional products that are processed through these new technologies.	1.606	4
20	Thanks to the novel food process technologies, small farmers can find the opportunity to market their citrus products and generate additional income.	1.542	3
12	Novel food process technologies will further diversify production activities and practices.	1.439	3
28	The use of novel food process technologies has a positive impact on the environment since it involves the consumption of processed products.	1.263	3
40	Adopting novel food process technologies can result in high transaction and production costs.	1.144	2
27	I believe using of novel food process technologies should involve the choice of environmentally-friendly distribution channels for the related output products, such as trains, e-bikes, etc.	-1.067	-2
5	Novel food process technologies can improve the skills development of employees.	-1.444	-3
30	Novel food process technologies can be a tool for improving good governance and coordination among value chain stakeholders that are engaged in more sustainable food systems.	-1.573	-3
31	Novel food process technologies adoption should be accompanied by consideration for not excluding less empowered stakeholders within the innovation value chain.	-1.763	-3
22	The use of novel food process technology for the production of the primary output produce should require efficient use of energy, water and materials.	-1.780	-4
39	It is possible to encounter bureaucratic obstacles in adopting novel food process technologies.	-2.058	-4

3.2 Results of Q-methodology analysis in Greece

Second Q methodology workshop was held with 27 stakeholders at the Greek Living Lab on July 4, 2023, in Greece. This workshop aimed to explore the thoughts and perspectives of stakeholders with different characteristics on adopting novel food process technologies in Greece.

Table 8, called P-set, in which the participants' information is included in the Q methodology, is given below. According to the composition of the P set, Factor 1 represents five farmers, five research/governmental organizations, two consumers, and two industries. Factor 2 represents three industries and one consumer. Factor 3 represents two industries, one consumer, one farmer, and three research/governmental organizations. The 27 Q-sorts were entered into the PQ Method software for data analysis—twenty-five of the 27 Q-sorts loaded significantly in the factors. The two Q-sorts that did not significantly in any factor were not used for further analysis, but they might represent unique viewpoints not captured in this research. From the 25 remainder, Q-sorts were used to constitute three factors. This case study used principal component analysis (PCA) and varimax rotation for factor analysis. The PCA allowed the specificity of each type and their commonalities to be considered. Therefore, stakeholders with similar opinions were grouped into one factor. Specifically, they explained the following factor loadings, or correlations between the interviews: the first factor (F1) accounted for 22% of the variance and is associated with 14 stakeholders; the second factor (F2) accounted for 10% of the variance and is associated with four stakeholders; the third factor (F3) accounted for the 14% of the variance and is associated with seven stakeholders. Only two sorts were not associated with any factor (Table 8). We identified three different viewpoints of the participants about the elements that would facilitate participants' adoption of the novel food process technologies. The selected three-factor solution accounted for 25 out of the 27 participants (92.59% of the sample) and explained 46% of the total variance.

Table 8 Composition of the P-set in Greece

No	Gender	Age	Type of stakeholder	Factors		
				1	2	3
1	M	53	Farmer	Factor 1		
2	M	24	Research/governmental organization	Factor 1		
3	F	74	Consumer		Factor 2	
4	M	74	Consumer	Factor 1		
5	M	27	Research/governmental organization	Factor 1		
6	M	55	Industry			Factor 3
7	F	27	Industry			Factor 3
8	F	29	Industry	Factor 1		
9	M	34	Industry			
10	M	57	Industry	Factor 1		

11	F	27	Industry		Factor 2	
12	M	49	Farmer	Factor 1		
13	F	29	Research/governmental organization	Factor 1		
14	F	39	Research/governmental organization			Factor 3
15	M	63	Consumer			Factor 3
16	F	34	Research/governmental organization	Factor 1		
17	M	50	Farmer	Factor 1		
18	F	45	Research/governmental organization			Factor 3
19	F	24	Industry		Factor 2	
20	F	30	Industry			
21	M	37	Farmer			Factor 3
22	F	48	Research/governmental organization	Factor 1		
23	M	32	Research/governmental organization			Factor 3
24	F	52	Farmer	Factor 1		
25	M	28	Farmer	Factor 1		
26	F	73	Consumer	Factor 1		
27	M	49	Industry		Factor 2	

Table 9 shows the factor loading per each Q-sort and asterisks and different colours indicate a defining sort for the corresponding factor. Factor 1 explains 22%, Factor 2 explains 10% and Factor 3 explains 14% of the total variance. All factors together explain 46% of the total variance.

Table 9 Factor matrix with an X indicating a defining sort in Greece

Q sort	Participant code	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3
1	040701	0.6314*	0.0100	0.0796
2	040702	0.6684*	-0.3461	0.0048
3	040703	-0.0219	-0.5810*	0.3298
4	040704	0.4105*	-0.1646	0.2114
5	040705	0.4333*	-0.1157	0.3595
6	040706	0.2279	0.2174	0.5242*

7	040707	0.1393	0.1444	0.5064*
8	040708	0.5738*	0.3497	0.2247
9	040709	0.5736	0.5633	0.1243
10	040710	0.4077*	0.1705	0.1564
11	040711	0.2044	-0.3133*	-0.2356
12	040712	0.6777*	-0.0129	0.4522
13	040713	0.6782*	0.0695	0.4419
14	040714	0.2398	0.0442	0.5565*
15	040715	-0.0345	0.3457	0.7101*
16	040716	0.6931*	0.1342	0.2434
17	040717	0.6698*	0.3580	0.1878
18	040718	0.2198	-0.0458	0.5947*
19	040719	-0.0591	0.6908*	0.2076
20	040720	0.0612	0.1229	0.1971
21	040721	0.1593	-0.3068	0.6063*
22	040722	0.8072*	-0.1686	0.1144
23	040723	0.2950	-0.0763	0.5403*
24	040724	0.6875*	0.2422	0.0944
25	040725	0.4304*	-0.0694	0.2883
26	040726	0.5970*	0.2533	-0.5086
27	040727	0.1840	0.7321*	0.0355
% Expl. Var.		22	10	14

Table 10 shows factor Q sort values for each statement in Greece. The factor arrays indicate the level of agreement or disagreement of each factor with each statement used for the Q-sort. The range is from -4 (strongly disagree) to 4 (strongly agree). Table 3 also shows significance levels of statements. According to Table 3, except for statements 2, 4, 5, 18, 25, 29 and 32, all statements were significant at the %1 and 5% levels. Of these, only statement 25 was significant at the 5% level but meaningless at 1%, and the remaining statements were meaningless at 1% and 5%. Significant values for each factor are shown with a different colour, and expressions with an asterisk beside them indicate significance at the 1% level. If there is an asterisk in the 'significance level' line, the status expression is significant at the 1% level for all factors. Statements 8, 11, 20, 22, 23, 27 and 36 were significant at all significance levels and for all factors ($p < 0.01$ and $p < 0.05$).

Table 10 Factor Q sort values for each statement in Greece

No	Statements	Factor Arrays			Significance level
		1	2	3	
1	Novel food process technologies can raise awareness and interest in local communities on the potential of local and traditional products that are processed through these new technologies.	0	3*	-2	
2	Novel food process technologies can improve the quality of consumer lives, offering tastier and healthier products while enhancing the working conditions of processors.	1	2	2	
3	Novel food process technologies promote and connect the importance of sustainability to general culture.	2	4	3	
4	Novel food process technologies offer a better - and novel - juice product by reducing the sugars while maintaining their natural profile of vitamins, minerals and fibres.	3	3	4	
5	Novel food process technologies can improve the skills development of employees.	0	0	0	
6	Novel food process technologies improve the awareness of the sustainability of workers in the value chains, consumers and stakeholders.	0	2*	-1	
7	Novel food process technologies might put aside traditional processing practices and reduce workforce needs.	0	3*	-2	
8	Novel food process technologies can improve the quality of life of workers in the food industry and the personal development of workers, producers and stakeholders concerning sustainability.	-2*	2*	-4*	*
9	Citrus/pomegranate growing protects and preserves rural territories' historical and cultural values.	0	1	-2*	
10	Novel food products using green technologies can help people have a balanced diet.	1	2	-2*	
11	Novel food process technologies will increase opportunities for partnership with different stakeholders of value chains.	2*	4*	-1*	*
12	Novel food process technologies will further diversify production activities and practices.	1	0	0	
13	I believe novel food process technologies allow for more environment-friendly and cost-effective production.	3	0*	1	
14	Novel food process technologies and practices must be communicated appropriately to targeted customers, in order to transfer knowledge and awareness to purchasers	2*	-1	1	

	and consumers about their innovative value and potential for green production.				
15	Novel food process technologies allow for increasing and better targeting of environmentally-friendly customers with economically accessible products.	1*	-2	-1	
16	For applying novel food process technologies, it is necessary to have a supply of sustainable/environmentally-friendly resources (such as organic raw materials and environmentally sustainable resource supply).	-1*	-3	-3	
17	Food products obtained from novel food process technologies will need appropriate distribution channels such as supermarkets, wholesalers, etc.	-1	-2	-4*	
18	I think the cost of novel food process technologies should be lower than traditional technologies as the energy use should decrease.	-1	0	0	
19	Producer revenues will increase as the sale price of novel food products will be relatively higher than those ones obtained from traditional technologies, especially with respect to costs.	-3	1*	-3	
20	Thanks to the novel food process technologies, small farmers can find the opportunity to market their citrus products and generate additional income.	-4*	1*	-2*	*
21	Novel food process technologies should be used through efficient and sustainable sourcing of energy and water.	3	-2*	2	
22	The use of novel food process technology for the production of the primary output produce should require efficient use of energy, water and materials.	4*	-1*	2*	*
23	Novel food process technologies help the efficient use of energy, water and materials in the production phase and waste reduction and efficient practices in the consumption phase.	4*	-1*	2*	*
24	Novel food process technologies allow the spread and trigger of other production and consumption practices that avoid waste and encourage the reuse of technology and materials.	2	-2*	2	
25	Consumers using food products obtained from novel food process technologies are more aware of the environmental impact of their consumption patterns and apply environmentally-friendly and circular behaviours.	-1	-1	0	
26	The use of novel food process technologies should involve the use of materials obtained from sustainable supply chains.	0*	-3	-3	

27	I believe using of novel food process technologies should involve the choice of environmentally-friendly distribution channels for the related output products, such as trains, e-bikes, etc.	0*	-4*	-1*	*
28	The use of novel food process technologies has a positive impact on the environment since it involves the consumption of processed products.	-1	0	1*	
29	Using novel food process technologies can bring environmental benefits in producing juices and smoothies because they reduce waste products and energy consumption.	2	2	2	
30	Novel food process technologies can be a tool for improving good governance and coordination among value chain stakeholders that are engaged in more sustainable food systems.	-2	-2	0*	
31	Novel food process technologies adoption should be accompanied by consideration for not excluding less empowered stakeholders within the innovation value chain.	1	0	4*	
32	Novel food process technologies adoption can contribute to engagement in more ethical value chains.	0	0	0	
33	Novel food process technologies adoption can contribute to overall complex sustainability strategies within the value chain.	1	1	3	
34	Novel food process technologies can provide protocols to regulate rules and standards for processors and stakeholders in the value chains.	-2	-1	3*	
35	Novel food process technologies can improve traceability and measurement systems across the processing dynamics (including the traceability of different processes of stakeholders).	-3*	1	1	
36	Novel food process technologies can improve the transparency of the flow of information through innovative and digital processes and practices.	-2*	1*	0*	*
37	Adopting novel food process technologies involve costs and risks regarding low coordination, adaptation of the new technology for producers and consumers (acceptability), excessive bureaucracy, exclusion and power imbalances.	-4	-3	-1*	
38	Adopting novel food process technologies can benefit coordination, collaboration and transparency with other stakeholders engaged in the value chain.	-1	0	1	
39	It is possible to encounter bureaucratic obstacles in adopting novel food process technologies.	-3	-4	-1*	

40	Adopting novel food process technologies can result in high transaction and production costs.	-2	-1	0	
----	---	----	----	---	--

According to Table 11, factor arrays are divided into themes which underpin the novel food process technologies. The darker green colour illustrates a more substantial degree of agreement, the darker grey colour a more robust disagreement and the yellow colour a neutral. According to this, it is clear that factors have different interests for different statements. For example, within the theme of social, it has been observed that while Factor 1 shows a high interest that new food processing technologies can raise awareness and interest in local communities about the potential of local and traditional products, Factor 3 does not show much interest in this (S: 1). On the other hand, it is a positive result that all factors think that the nutritional value of fruit juice produced from novel food processing technologies will be higher than standard fruit juices (S: 4). Within the theme of economics, Factor 1 and Factor 3 do not strongly agree (-3) with the idea that producer incomes will increase since the selling price of novel food products will be relatively higher than those obtained from traditional technologies, especially in terms of cost; however, it has been observed that Factor 2 slightly agrees with this idea (+1). Although the degree of participation is different, all three factors think that when implementing new food processing technologies, there is no need to have sustainable/environmentally friendly resources and that appropriate distribution channels are optional to market these products (S: 16 and S: 17).

Within the theme of environment, Factor 1 and Factor 3 think that novel food process technologies should be used through efficient and sustainable energy and water resources; it has been observed that Factor 2, which predominantly represents the food industry group, does not agree with this statement (S: 21). In the theme of governance statements, all factors consider that excessive bureaucracy and cost risks will not arise when adopting new food processing technologies (S: 37 and S: 39).

Table 11 Factor arrays by themes in Greece

Theme	No	Statements	Factor Arrays		
			1	2	3
Social	1	Novel food process technologies can raise awareness and interest in local communities on the potential of local and traditional products that are processed through these new technologies.	0	3	-2
	2	Novel food process technologies can improve the quality of consumer lives, offering tastier and healthier products while enhancing the working conditions of processors.	1	2	2
	3	Novel food process technologies promote and connect the importance of sustainability to general culture.	2	4	3
	4	Novel food process technologies offer a better - and novel - juice product by reducing the sugars while maintaining their natural profile of vitamins, minerals and fibres.	3	3	4
	5	Novel food process technologies can improve the skills development of employees.	0	0	0
	6	Novel food process technologies improve the awareness of the sustainability of workers in the value chains, consumers and stakeholders.	0	2	-1
	7	Novel food process technologies might put aside traditional processing practices and reduce workforce needs.	0	3	-2
	8	Novel food process technologies can improve the quality of life of workers in the food industry and the personal development of workers, producers and stakeholders concerning sustainability.	-2	2	-4
	9	Citrus/pomegranate growing protects and preserves rural territories' historical and cultural values.	0	1	-2
	10	Novel food products using green technologies can help people have a balanced diet.	1	2	-2
Economics	11	Novel food process technologies will increase opportunities for partnership with different stakeholders of value chains.	2	4	-1
	12	Novel food process technologies will further diversify production activities and practices.	1	0	0
	13	I believe novel food process technologies allow for more environment-friendly and cost-effective production.	3	0	1

	14	Novel food process technologies and practices must be communicated appropriately to targeted customers, in order to transfer knowledge and awareness to purchasers and consumers about their innovative value and potential for green production.	2	-1	1
	15	Novel food process technologies allow for increasing and better targeting of environmentally-friendly customers with economically accessible products.	1	-2	-1
	16	For applying novel food process technologies, it is necessary to have a supply of sustainable/environmentally-friendly resources (such as organic raw materials and environmentally sustainable resource supply).	-1	-3	-3
	17	Food products obtained from novel food process technologies will need appropriate distribution channels such as supermarkets, wholesalers, etc.	-1	-2	-4
	18	I think the cost of novel food process technologies should be lower than traditional technologies as the energy use should decrease.	-1	0	0
	19	Producer revenues will increase as the sale price of novel food products will be relatively higher than those ones obtained from traditional technologies, especially with respect to costs.	-3	1	-3
	20	Thanks to the novel food process technologies, small farmers can find the opportunity to market their citrus products and generate additional income.	-4	1	-2
Environmental	21	Novel food process technologies should be used through efficient and sustainable sourcing of energy and water.	3	-2	2
	22	The use of novel food process technology for the production of the primary output produce should require efficient use of energy, water and materials.	4	-1	2
	23	Novel food process technologies help the efficient use of energy, water and materials in the production phase and waste reduction and efficient practices in the consumption phase.	4	-1	2
	24	Novel food process technologies allow the spread and trigger of other production and consumption practices that avoid waste and encourage the reuse of technology and materials.	2	-2	2
	25	Consumers using food products obtained from novel food process technologies are more aware of the environmental impact of their consumption patterns and apply environmentally-friendly and circular behaviors.	-1	-1	0

	26	The use of novel food process technologies should involve the use of materials obtained from sustainable supply chains.	0	-3	-3
	27	I believe using of novel food process technologies should involve the choice of environmentally-friendly distribution channels for the related output products, such as trains, e-bikes, etc.	0	-4	-1
	28	The use of novel food process technologies has a positive impact on the environment since it involves the consumption of processed products.	-1	0	1
	29	Using novel food process technologies can bring environmental benefits in producing juices and smoothies because they reduce waste products and energy consumption.	2	2	2
Governance	30	Novel food process technologies can be a tool for improving good governance and coordination among value chain stakeholders that are engaged in more sustainable food systems.	-2	-2	0
	31	Novel food process technologies adoption should be accompanied by consideration for not excluding less empowered stakeholders within the innovation value chain.	1	0	4
	32	Novel food process technologies adoption can contribute to engagement in more ethical value chains.	0	0	0
	33	Novel food process technologies adoption can contribute to overall complex sustainability strategies within the value chain.	1	1	3
	34	Novel food process technologies can provide protocols to regulate rules and standards for processors and stakeholders in the value chains.	-2	-1	3
	35	Novel food process technologies can improve traceability and measurement systems across the processing dynamics (including the traceability of different processes of stakeholders).	-3	1	1
	36	Novel food process technologies can improve the transparency of the flow of information through innovative and digital processes and practices.	-2	1	0
	37	Adopting novel food process technologies involve costs and risks regarding low coordination, adaptation of the new technology for producers and consumers (acceptability), excessive bureaucracy, exclusion and power imbalances.	-4	-3	-1
	38	Adopting novel food process technologies can benefit coordination, collaboration and transparency with other stakeholders engaged in the value chain.	-1	0	1
	39	It is possible to encounter bureaucratic obstacles in adopting novel food process technologies.	-3	-4	-1

	40	Adopting novel food process technologies can result in high transaction and production costs.	-2	-1	0
--	----	---	----	----	---

Perspectives

There is no specific stakeholder typology with each factor; however, it is noted that representatives of governmental organizations and farmers emphasized the environmental and economic importance of novel food process technologies. The discourse structure indicated that novel food process technologies are seen from stakeholders' diverse perspectives. Surprisingly, all three perceptions were represented by various stakeholders, and not all sector respondents shared the same perception. Although the identified perceptions were well distinguished, several areas of agreement were identified, which can serve as a common ground for discussion. Finally, the findings revealed Greece's leading social, economic, environmental, and governance challenges.

Respondents of Perception 1 argued that they care about a sustainable environment and that efficient use of resources (such as water, electricity, and energy) may be the most crucial benefit of novel food process technologies. Participants in Perception 1 think that novel food process technologies will contribute to producing healthier products and help people have a more balanced diet. Stakeholders in this group think that industries using novel food process technologies have the opportunity to produce cost-effectively. However, according to their opinion, the producers who sell these products and small farmers who market their citrus products will not have a higher income. This group considers that adopting novel food process technologies will not lead to high transaction and production costs, nor will it involve high costs and risks in terms of excessive bureaucracy or coordination.

Perception 1 and Perception 3 contained the closest views, mainly because the environmental benefits that novel food process technologies can create are compatible with the sustainability goal. The stakeholders in Factor 2 are far from this idea. The main reason for this is that Factor 2 mainly includes industries, and they give priority to the social and economic benefits of novel food process technologies. Nevertheless, the study results show that all factors have some expressions in which they decide together, positive, and negative. Since these joint statements include all stakeholders, they can indicate the existence of opportunities and potential risks that may arise in adopting new technology.

Perspective 1

Factor 1 explains 22% of the study variance, and the eigenvalue is 8.800. Fourteen participants are significantly associated with this factor. They are from various backgrounds, such as farmers, industries, citizens, governmental organizations, and academia. The average age of stakeholders in Factor 1 is 44.78, and according to their gender, it consists of 8 men and six women. Factor 1 has been simultaneously associated with environmental benefits while concerning economic and social benefits. Environmental benefits such as efficient use of energy, water and materials and waste reduction are significant to this group (S23 and S22: +4, S21: +3), and they believe that adopting novel food process technologies will not involve costs and risks regarding low coordination, the adaptation of the new technology for producers and consumers (acceptability), excessive bureaucracy, exclusion, and power imbalances (S37: -4). They do not believe that small farmers will have the opportunity to market their citrus products and generate additional income (S20: -4). However, they feel that novel food process technologies allow for more environment-friendly and cost-effective production (S13: +3). The taste and high nutritional value are also crucial for this factor (S4:

+3). For a social benefit, factor 1 thinks that novel food process technologies can promote the importance of sustainability and are relevant to the general culture (S3: +2). Further, there is a belief that novel food process technologies can increase the opportunities for partnerships with different stakeholders of value chains (S11: +2).

Perspective 2

Factor 2 explains 10% of the study variance, and the eigenvalue is 4.00. Four participants are significantly associated with this factor. They are from food industry, and only one consumer. The average age of stakeholders in Factor 2 is 43.5, and according to their gender, it consists of 3 women and a man. The Factor 2 has been associated with social themes. The environmental benefits of novel food process technologies are less attractive to this group. They do not consider environmental issues but believe that using novel food process technologies can bring environmental benefits in producing juices and smoothies because they reduce waste products and energy consumption (S29: +2). This group mainly focuses on benefits to themselves or society and protects some cultural aspects. For example, they believe that novel food process technologies promote and connect the importance of sustainability to general culture (S3: +4), or citrus/pomegranate growing protects and preserves rural territories' historical and cultural values (S9: +2).

Perspective 3

Factor 3 explains 14% of the study variance, and the eigenvalue is 5.600. Seven participants are significantly associated with this factor. They are from various backgrounds, such as industries, governmental organizations, farmers, and consumers. Factor 3 represents two industries, one consumer, one farmer and three research/governmental organizations. For Factor 3, the environmental benefits of novel food process technologies, such as efficient energy use, water and materials and waste reduction, are important (S23, S29, S24 and S21: +2). In addition, it has been determined that governance themes are important for this group, such as 'novel food process technologies adoption should be accompanied by consideration for not excluding less empowered stakeholders within the innovation value chain' (S31: +4). This group believes that novel food process technologies will contribute to sustainability strategies in the value chain (S33: +3) and provide protocols that set rules and standards for processors and stakeholders in value chains (S34: +3). This group considers that it is unnecessary to have different distribution channels for the marketing of food products obtained from new food processing technologies and to have environmentally friendly resources in applying this technology (S17: -4 and S16: -3).

Figure 6 Idealized Q-sort for Factor 1 in Greece

Strongly disagree	-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3	Strongly agree
	37. Adopting novel food process technologies involve costs and risks regarding low ...	39. It is possible to encounter bureaucratic obstacles in adopting novel...	8. Novel food process technologies can improve the quality of life ...	16. For applying novel food process technologies...	9.Citrus / pomegranate growing protects and preserves rural ...	2. Novel food process technologies can improve ...	24. Novel food process technologies allow the spread ...	21. Novel food process technologies should be used ...	23. Novel food process technologies help the efficient use of energy, water ...
	20. Thanks to the novel food process technologies, small farmers ...	35. Novel food process technologies can improve traceability and measurement ...	34. Novel food process technologies can provide protocols ...	17. Food products obtained from novel food process...	27. I believe using of novel food process technologies should involve ...	12. Novel food process technologies will further diversify...	14. Novel food process technologies and practices ...	4. Novel food process technologies offer a better ...	22.The use of novel food process technology for the production ...
		19. Producer revenues will increase as the sale price of novel food...	30. Novel food process technologies can be a tool for improving good ...	25. Consumers using food products obtained from novel food...	26. The use of novel food process technologies should involve the use of ...	31. Novel food process technologies adoption should...	29. Using novel food process technologies can bring ...	13. I believe novel food process technologies allow for more ...	
			36. Novel food process technologies can improve the transparency ...	38. Adopting novel food process technologies ...	5. Novel food process technologies can improve the skills development ...	10. Novel food products using green technologies can help people...	11. Novel food process technologies will further diversify...		
			40. Adopting novel food process technologies can result in high ...	18. I think the cost of novel food process technologies...	32. Novel food process technologies adoption can contribute ...	33. Novel food process technologies adoption ...	3. Novel food process technologies promote...		
				28. The use of novel food process technologies ...	6. Novel food process technologies improve the awareness of the sustainability ...	15. Novel food process technologies allow for increasing ...			
					1.Novel food process technologies can raise awareness and interest in local...				
					7. Novel food process technologies might put aside traditional...				

Figure 7 Idealized Q-sort for Factor 2 in Greece

Strongly disagree

Strongly agree

-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3	4
27. I believe using of novel food process technologies should involve...	26. The use of novel food process technologies should involve...	30. Novel food process technologies can be a tool for improving good governance ...	34. Novel food process technologies can provide protocols to ...	31. Novel food process technologies adoption should be accompanied by consideration for ...	36. Novel food process technologies can improve the transparency ...	10. Novel food products using green technologies can help people have ...	7. Novel food process technologies might put aside traditional processing ...	3. Novel food process technologies promote and connect the importance of ...
39. It is possible to encounter bureaucratic ...	37. Adopting novel food process technologies ...	17. Food products obtained from novel food process ...	14. Novel food process technologies and practices ...	32. Novel food process technologies adoption can contribute ...	33. Novel food process technologies adoption ...	2. Novel food process technologies can improve the quality	4. Novel food process technologies offer a better - and novel...	11. Novel food process technologies will increase ...
	16. For applying novel food process technologies, it is necessary ...	15. Novel food process technologies allow for increasing and better targeting of ...	22. The use of novel food process technology for the production ...	12. Novel food process technologies will further diversify production activities and practices.	20. Thanks to the novel food process technologies, small farmers can find...	6. Novel food process technologies improve the awareness of the sustainability ...	1. Novel food process technologies can raise awareness and interest in local...	
		24. Novel food process technologies allow the spread and trigger ...	25. Consumers using food products obtained from ...	5. Novel food process technologies can improve the skills...	35. Novel food process technologies can improve...	8. Novel food process technologies can improve the quality		
		21. Novel food process technologies should be used through ...	23. Novel food process technologies help the efficient ...	38. Adopting novel food process technologies can benefit coordination...	9. Citrus /pomegranate growing protects ...	29. Using novel food process technologies can bring ...		
			40. Adopting novel food process technologies ...	18. I think the cost of novel food process technologies should	19. Producer revenues will increase as the sale price of ...			
				28. The use of novel food process technologies has a positive impact on the...				
				13. I believe novel food process technologies allow for more environment-friendly and cost-effective...				

Figure 8 Idealized Q-sort for Factor 3 in Greece

Strongly disagree

Strongly agree

-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3	4
17. Food products obtained from novel food process ...	16. For applying novel food process technologies ...	7. Novel food process technologies might put aside traditional ...	37. Adopting novel food process technologies ...	32. Novel food process technologies adoption can contribute to ...	28. The use of novel food process technologies has ...	23. Novel food process technologies help the efficient ...	34. Novel food process technologies can provide ...	31. Novel food process technologies adoption should be ...
8. Novel food process technologies can improve the ...	26. The use of novel food process technologies ...	1. Novel food process technologies can raise awareness and ...	15. Novel food process technologies allow for ...	30. Novel food process technologies can be a tool for improving ...	13. I believe novel food process technologies allow ...	29. Using novel food process technologies can bring ...	3. Novel food process technologies promote and ...	4. Novel food process technologies offer a better - and novel ...
	19. Producer revenues will increase as the ...	10. Novel food products using green technologies can help ...	11. Novel food process technologies will increase ...	25. Consumers using food products obtained from novel food ...	35. Novel food process technologies can improve ...	24. Novel food process technologies allow the spread ...	33. Novel food process technologies adoption ...	
		20. Thanks to the novel food process technologies, small...	39. It is possible to encounter bureaucratic ...	12. Novel food process technologies will further diversify production ...	38. Adopting novel food process technologies can ...	2. Novel food process technologies can improve the ...		
		9. Citrus /pomegranate growing protects and preserves rural...	27. I believe using of novel food process technologies ...	5. Novel food process technologies can improve the skills ...	22. The use of novel food process technology for the ...	21. Novel food process technologies should be used ...		
			6. Novel food process technologies improve the ...	40. Adopting novel food process technologies can result in high ...	14. Novel food process technologies and practices must...			
				36. Novel food process technologies can improve the transparency of the				
				18. I think the cost of novel food process technologies should be lower than traditional				

Table 12 contains the top six most-agree and most disagree statements from Factor 1 stakeholders' viewpoint. The statements that Factor 1 attaches the most importance to, respectively, are the statements that they think will provide environmental benefits of novel food process technologies. It was determined that the statements that Factor 1 gave the least importance to, were some governance statements.

Table 12 Factor 1 tops six most agree/most disagree statements in Greece

No	Statement	Z-score	Grid position
23	Novel food process technologies help the efficient use of energy, water and materials in the production phase, the waste reduction and efficient practices in the consumption phase.	1.817	4
22	The use of novel food process technologies for the production of the primary output produce should require efficient use of energy, water and materials.	1.728	4
21	Novel food process technologies should be used through efficient and sustainable sourcing of energy and water.	1.512	3
4	Novel food process technologies offer a better - and novel - juice product by reducing the sugars while maintaining their natural profile of vitamins, minerals and fibres.	1.410	3
13	I believe novel food process technologies allow for a more environmentally friendly and cost-effective production.	1.330	3
24	Novel food process technologies allow the spread and trigger of other production and consumption practices that avoid waste and encourage the reuse of technology and materials.	1.134	2
40	Adopting novel food process technologies can result in high transaction and production costs.	-1.153	-2
39	It is possible to encounter bureaucratic obstacles in adopting novel food process technologies.	-1.430	-3
35	Novel food process technologies can improve traceability and measurement systems across the processing dynamics (including the traceability of different processes of stakeholders).	-1.526	-3
19	Producer revenues will increase as the sale price of novel food products will be relatively higher than those ones obtained from traditional technologies, especially with respect to costs.	-1.563	-3
37	Adopting novel food process technologies involve costs and risks regarding low coordination, adaptation of the new technology for producers and consumers (acceptability), excessive bureaucracy, exclusion and power imbalances	-1.564	-4

20	Thanks to the novel food process technologies, small farmers can find the opportunity to market their citrus products and generate additional income.	-1.950	-4
----	---	--------	----

Table 13 contains the top six most-agree and most disagree statements from Factor 2 stakeholders' viewpoint. The statements that Factor 2 attaches the most importance to, respectively, are the statements that they think will provide social benefits of novel food process technologies. It was determined that the statements that Factor 2 gave the least importance to, were some environmental and governance statements.

Table 13 Factor 2 tops six most agree/most disagree statements in Greece

No	Statement	Z-score	Grid position
3	Novel food process technologies promote and connect the importance of sustainability to general culture.	1.959	4
11	Novel food process technologies will increase opportunities for partnership with different stakeholders of value chains.	1.832	4
7	Novel food process technologies might put aside traditional processing practices and reduce workforce needs.	1.525	3
4	Novel food process technologies offer a better - and novel - juice product by reducing the sugars while maintaining their natural profile of vitamins, minerals and fibres.	1.369	3
1	Novel food process technologies can raise awareness and interest in local communities on the potential of local and traditional products that are processed through these new technologies.	1.277	3
10	Novel food products using green technologies can help people have a balanced diet.	1.234	2
21	Novel food process technologies should be used through efficient and sustainable sourcing of energy and water.	-1.206	-2
26	The use of novel food process technologies should involve the use of materials obtained from sustainable supply chains.	-1.304	-3
37	Adopting novel food process technologies involve costs and risks regarding low coordination, adaptation of the new technology for producers and consumers (acceptability), excessive bureaucracy, exclusion and power imbalances.	-1.512	-3
16	For applying novel food process technologies, it is necessary to have a supply of sustainable/environmentally-friendly resources (such as organic raw materials and environmentally sustainable resource supply).	-1.597	-3

27	I believe using of novel food process technologies should involve the choice of environmentally-friendly distribution channels for the related output products, such as trains, e-bikes, etc.	-1.610	-4
39	It is possible to encounter bureaucratic obstacles in adopting novel food process technologies.	-1.701	-4

Table 14 contains the top six most-agree and most disagree statements from Factor 3 stakeholders' viewpoint. The statements that Factor 3 attaches the most importance to, respectively, are the statements that they think will provide governance and social benefits of novel food process technologies. It was determined that the statements that Factor 3 gave the least importance to, were some economic statements.

Table 14 Factor 3 tops six most agree/most disagree statements in Greece

No	Statement	Z-score	Grid position
31	Novel food process technologies adoption should be accompanied by consideration for not excluding less empowered stakeholders within the innovation value chain.	2.138	4
4	Novel food process technologies offer a better - and novel - juice product by reducing the sugars while maintaining their natural profile of vitamins, minerals and fibres.	1.578	4
34	Novel food process technologies can provide protocols to regulate rules and standards for processors and stakeholders in the value chains.	1.366	3
3	Novel food process technologies promote and connect the importance of sustainability to general culture.	1.342	3
33	Novel food process technologies adoption can contribute to overall complex sustainability strategies within the value chain.	1.137	3
23	Novel food process technologies help the efficient use of energy, water and materials in the production phase and waste reduction and efficient practices in the consumption phase.	1.112	2
9	Citrus/pomegranate growing protects and preserves rural territories' historical and cultural values.	-1.097	-2
16	For applying novel food process technologies, it is necessary to have a supply of sustainable/environmentally-friendly resources (such as organic raw materials and environmentally sustainable resource supply).	-1.142	-3
26	The use of novel food process technologies should involve the use of materials obtained from sustainable supply chains.	-1.182	-3

19	Producer revenues will increase as the sale price of novel food products will be relatively higher than those ones obtained from traditional technologies, especially with respect to costs.	-1.329	-3
17	Food products obtained from novel food process technologies will need appropriate distribution channels such as supermarkets, wholesalers, etc.	-2.021	-4
8	Novel food process technologies can improve the quality of life of workers in the food industry and the personal development of workers, producers and stakeholders concerning sustainability.	-2.087	-4

3.3 Comparison the perspectives of stakeholders in Greece and Malta

In this section, the perspectives of stakeholders in Greece and Malta on the novel food process technologies are compared. This comparison was made through four categories: social, economic, environmental and governance.

According to **social category**:

- While most stakeholders in Malta believe that novel food process technologies can increase awareness and interest in local communities about the potential of local and traditional products processed with these new technologies, most stakeholders in Greece do not believe (S1).
- While most stakeholders in Greece think that novel food process technologies can improve the quality of consumers' lives by offering tastier and healthier products while enhancing the working conditions of processors, stakeholders in Malta disagree with this perspective (S2).
- While most stakeholders in Greece agree that novel food process technologies promote the importance of sustainability and connect it to the general culture, stakeholders in Malta feel differently (S3).
- Stakeholders in both Greece and Malta agree that novel food process technologies offer a better, new juice product by reducing sugar while preserving the natural vitamin, mineral and fibre profile (S4). This situation is an opportunity to develop marketing strategies emphasizing that the new product is healthier than standard ones.
- While it was determined that most of the participants in Malta did not think that novel food process technologies could increase the skill development of employees, it was determined that Greece had both a negative perspective on this issue, as in Malta, and, unlike Malta, positive views (S5).
- While it was found that most participants in Malta did not believe that novel food process technologies increased the awareness of employees, consumers, and stakeholders in value chains about sustainability, in Greece, it was found that there were three different dominant views on this issue (S6).
- Most respondents in Malta and Greece do not think novel food process technologies can sideline traditional processing practices and reduce labour needs (S7).

- It was found that the majority of respondents in both Greece and Malta did not believe that novel food process technologies could improve the quality of life of workers in the food industry and the personal development of employees, producers and stakeholders regarding sustainability (S8).
- It has been determined that stakeholders of both countries share different positive and negative opinions on whether citrus/pomegranate cultivation can protect the historical and cultural values of rural regions (S9).
- Lastly, it was found that in Malta and Greece, most respondents thought novel food products using green technologies could help people maintain a balanced diet (S10).

According to the **economic category**:

- It has been found that stakeholders in Greece and Malta share more common ideas regarding the economic aspects of the novel technology. Most respondents in both countries believe that novel food process technologies will increase partnership opportunities with different value chain stakeholders (S11).
- It was found that most participants in both countries think that novel food process technologies will further diversify production activities and practices (S12).
- It was found that most participants in both countries believe that novel food process technologies enable more environmentally friendly and cost-effective production (S13).
- Most participants in each country agreed that novel food process technologies and practices should be appropriately communicated to target customers to convey information and awareness to buyers and consumers about their innovative value and green production potential (S14).
- Most respondents in Greece and Malta agree that novel food process technologies allow greater targeting and better targeting of environmentally friendly customers with economically accessible products (S15).
- The majority of respondents in both countries think that implementing novel food process technologies does not require sourcing sustainable/environmentally friendly resources (such as organic raw materials and environmentally sustainable sourcing) (S16).
- In both countries, most participants do not think food products obtained from novel food process technologies will need appropriate distribution channels such as supermarkets, wholesalers, etc. (S17).
- In both countries, most respondents do not think the cost of novel food process technologies will be lower than traditional technologies because energy use should be reduced (S18).
- Most stakeholders in both countries do not believe that the sales prices of novel food products will impact increasing producer incomes, especially since they will be relatively higher in terms of cost than those obtained with traditional technologies (S19).
- While stakeholders in Greece do not think that small farmers will have the opportunity to market their citrus products and earn additional income thanks to novel food process technologies, stakeholders in Malta have two different views (S20).

According to the **environmental category**:

- The vast majority of respondents in both countries agree that novel food processing technologies should be used through efficient and sustainable energy and water supply (S21).
- Most respondents in both countries agreed that using novel food process technology to produce primary output should require efficient use of energy, water and materials (S22).
- Most participants in Greece agree that novel food process technologies help efficiently use energy, water, and materials in the production phase, reducing waste and efficient practices in the consumption phase. However, it was determined that the participants in Malta were between two different views (S23).
- Most respondents in both countries think that novel food process technologies enable the spread and trigger of other production and consumption practices that prevent waste and encourage the reuse of technologies and materials (S24).
- It was found that most participants in both countries did not think that consumers who use food products obtained from novel food process technologies are more aware of the environmental impacts of their consumption patterns and exhibit environmentally friendly and circular behaviour (S25).
- While most participants in Greece did not think that novel food process technologies should include using materials obtained from sustainable supply chains, participants in Malta were found to abstain from this issue (S26).
- It was found that most respondents in both countries do not believe that novel food process technologies should include the choice of environmentally friendly distribution channels for the relevant output products, such as trains, e-bikes, etc. (S27).
- Most respondents in Malta do not think that using novel food process technologies positively impacts the environment, as it involves consuming processed products. However, in Greece, respondents have different views on this issue (S28).
- Most respondents in both countries think that novel food process technologies can bring environmental benefits in producing juices and smoothies, reducing waste products and energy consumption (S29).

According to the **governance category**:

- most respondents in both countries, novel food process technologies cannot improve good management and coordination among value chain stakeholders interested in more sustainable food systems (S30).
- While the majority of respondents in Malta do not believe that adopting novel food process technologies should be accompanied by consideration of not excluding less empowered stakeholders in the innovation value chain, the majority of respondents in Greece do (S31).
- Most respondents from both countries do not think that adopting novel food process technologies can further contribute to participation in ethical value chains (S32).

- Most stakeholders in Greece think that adopting novel food process technologies can contribute to overall complex sustainability strategies in the value chain. However, stakeholders in Malta seem ambivalent on this issue (S33).
- It was found that most respondents in both countries do not believe that novel food process technologies can provide protocols that regulate rules and standards for processors and stakeholders in value chains (S34).
- It was found that most of the respondents in both countries did not think that novel food process technologies could improve traceability and measurement systems across processing dynamics (including traceability of different stakeholders' processes) (S35).
- Most respondents in both countries do not think novel food process technologies can increase information flow transparency through innovative and digital processes and applications (S36).
- Most respondents in both countries do not think adopting novel food process technologies involves costs and risks, such as low coordination, adaptation of new technology for producers and consumers (acceptability), excessive bureaucracy, exclusion and power imbalances (S37).
- The dominant view among participants in both countries is that they do not foresee that adopting novel food process technologies will benefit coordination, cooperation and transparency with other stakeholders in the value chain (S38).
- Most participants in Greece and nearly half in Malta do not think it is possible to encounter bureaucratic obstacles in adopting novel food process technologies (S39).
- Most respondents in Greece and half in Malta stated that they did not think adopting novel food process technologies could lead to high processing and production costs (S40).

4. Conclusions

The main purpose of this report is to identify bottlenecks in the diffusion of innovations in the value chain. Under this main purpose, Q methodology was used to explore stakeholders' perspectives on new technology. Diffusion of innovation is a complex process because individuals do not directly adopt innovation as soon as they hear about it. In order for an innovation to be adopted, it must have certain characteristics such as relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability and observability.

When the Q methodology results in both countries are evaluated in general, it has been determined that stakeholders in Malta and Greece have both familiar and different thoughts and perspectives about novel food process technologies. Exploring the similar and different perspectives of stakeholders simultaneously reveals the obstacles and opportunities to the diffusion of technology.

A variety of barriers can obstruct the adoption of a technology. The cost of the novel food process technologies can be a barrier for Greek stakeholders and Maltese stakeholders. According to Q-methodology results, most farmers and industries doubt that the cost of novel food process technologies will be lower than traditional technologies. In addition, nearly all stakeholders do not believe producer revenues will increase if they accept novel food process technologies. According to the *Diffusion of Innovations Theory* (Rogers et al., 2014), the degree of relative advantages depends on economic profitability, social prestige, or other

benefits. In Greece and Malta, stakeholders are still determining the economic profitability of novel food process technologies. In order to eliminate cost concerns in the diffusion and adoption of novel technology, it will be helpful to conduct a cost-benefit analysis. Another barrier, as determined from the participants' statements during the Q study and workshop, was that the participants found the new technology complicated. Addressing their lack of knowledge and providing them with opportunities to try these new technologies can help resolve this barrier. Food industry professionals, retailers, farmers, and citizens/consumers who need more knowledge about new technologies or are being trained to use these technologies can help the diffusion process.

Individuals can resist change, especially if they are satisfied with existing processes and technologies. Resistance to change can be a significant barrier, mainly as stakeholders in Malta have been observed to be more satisfied with existing technologies and do not think they will provide more benefits for people working in the food industry. Limited resources can also be a barrier that can make it difficult for small and medium-sized businesses to invest in and adopt new technologies, especially given that stakeholders in both countries have concerns about cost. Competitiveness and market dynamics can also be barriers affecting technology diffusion and adoption. Companies may hesitate to adopt new technology if they perceive that their competitors are not doing so or are unsure of the market's demand. Therefore, it is important to introduce the new technology and integrate as many stakeholders as possible into these introductions at this stage. Again, depending on this situation, some organizations may want to avoid risk and be reluctant to resort to unproven technologies. They may choose to stick with traditional technologies that already exist rather than adopting something new and untested. In this case, the degree of risk tolerance can also be a significant obstacle. Apart from all these, if individuals have had a bad experience with a new technology in the past, this will emerge as a significant obstacle to the spread and adoption of the technology.

A new technology is more straightforward to adopt and diffuse when it adapts to local culture and habits. The fact that all stakeholders in Greece believe that new food processing technologies promote the importance of sustainability and associate it with the general culture is an advantage in the diffusion of this new technology. However, the fact that stakeholders in Malta do not associate the new technology with the general culture can be seen as a barrier to the diffusion of this technology. It has been found that stakeholders in Greece think that new technology has more social benefits than stakeholders in Malta. Still, stakeholders in both countries have some common views. The fact that stakeholders in Greece and Malta think that new food processing technologies have health benefits and can help people have a balanced diet shows that they think new food technologies are more advantageous for health, which emerges as an opportunity to adopt technology. Although there are many regulations and standards in the food sector, stakeholders in both countries do not think that adopting new food processing technologies will involve costs and risks such as low coordination, excessive bureaucracy, exclusion and power imbalances. This result proves that the possibility of a barrier in this regard will be low. Highlighting environmental benefits may be effective in adopting technology, as stakeholders in Greece and Malta think the new technology will provide a more environmentally friendly production and use resources more effectively. Emphasizing environmental benefits and green practices is a

significant opportunity as it can help reduce the carbon footprint in the food industry. However, it should not be forgotten that the economic benefits of the new technology are at the forefront for stakeholders in Malta, while the social and environmental benefits are at the forefront for Greece. Despite all these barriers, it should not be forgotten that personal characteristics, socio-demographic characteristics of individuals and cultural factors are also influential in the spread and adoption of innovations.

References

- Amaruzaman, S., Leimona, B., Van Noordwijk, M., & Lusiana, B. (2017). Discourses on the performance gap of agriculture in a green economy: a Q-methodology study in Indonesia. *International Journal of Biodiversity Science, Ecosystem Services & Management*, 13(1), 233-247. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21513732.2017.1331264>
- Baker, R., Thompson, C., & Mannion, R. (2006). Q methodology in health economics. *Journal of Health Services Research & Policy*, 11(1), 38-45. <https://doi.org/10.1258/135581906775094217>
- Brown, S.R. (1980). Political subjectivity: Applications of Q methodology in political science. New Haven: Yale University Press.
- Brown, S. R., Durning, D. W., & Selden, S. C. (2008). Q methodology. *Public Administration and Public Policy-New York-*, 134, 721.
- Bumbudsanpharoke, W., Moran, D., & Hall, C. (2009). Exploring perspectives of environmental best management practices in Thai agriculture: An application of Q-methodology. *Environmental Conservation*, 36(3), 225-234. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0376892909990397>
- Chinnis, A. S., Paulson, D. J., & Davis, S. M. (2001). Using Q methodology to assess the needs of emergency medicine support staff employees. *The Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 20(2), 197-203. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0736-4679\(00\)00304-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0736-4679(00)00304-8)
- Davies, B. B., Blackstock, K., & Rauschmayer, F. (2005). "Recruitment", "composition", and "mandate" issues in deliberative processes: Should we focus on arguments rather than individuals? *Environment and Planning C: Government and Policy*, 23(4), 599-615.
- Durning, D., & Osuna, W. (1994). Policy analysts' roles and value orientations: An empirical investigation using Q methodology. *Journal of Policy Analysis and Management*, 13(4), 629-657. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3325491>
- Eden, S., Donaldson, A., & Walker, G. (2005). Structuring subjectivities? Using Q methodology in human geography. *Area*, 37(4), 413-422. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-4762.2005.00641x>

- Frantzi, S., Carter, N. T., & Lovett, J. C. (2009). Exploring discourses on international environmental regime effectiveness with Q methodology: A case study of the Mediterranean Action Plan. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 90(1), 177–186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2007.08.013>
- Gen, S., & Wright, A. C. (2018). Strategies of policy advocacy organizations and their theoretical affinities: evidence from Q-methodology. *Policy Studies Journal*, 46(2), 298-326. <https://doi.org/10.1111/psj.12167>
- Hermelingmeier, V., & Nicholas, K. A. (2017). Identifying five different perspectives on the ecosystem services concept using Q methodology. *Ecological Economics*, 136, 255-265. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2017.01.006>
- Jeffares, S., & Skelcher, C. (2011). Democratic subjectivities in network governance: A Q methodology study. *Public Administration*, 89(4), 1253–1273.
- Lehrer, N., & Sneegas, G. (2018). Beyond polarization: Using Q methodology to explore stakeholders' views on pesticide use, and related risks for agricultural workers, in Washington State's tree fruit industry. *Agriculture and Human Values*, 35, 131-147. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10460-017-9810-z>
- McKeown, B., & Thomas, D. (1988). Q Methodology. *Series: Quantitative Applications in the Social Sciences (Second Edition 2013)*, 66.
- McParland, J., Hezseltine, L., Serpell, M., Eccleston, C., & Stenner, P. (2011). An investigation of constructions of justice and injustice in chronic pain: A Q-methodology approach. *Journal of Health Psychology*, 16(6), 873-883. <https://doi.org/10.1177/135910531039>
- Millar, J. D., Mason, H., & Kidd, L. (2022). What is Q methodology?. *Evidence-Based Nursing*, 25(3), 77-78. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/ebnurs-2022-103568>
- Nijnik, M., Nijnik, A., & Bizikova, L. (2009). Analysing the development of small-scale forestry in Central and Eastern Europe. *Small-Scale Forestry*, 8(2), 159–174.
- Ramlo, S. E., & Newman, I. (2011). Q Methodology and its position in the mixed-methods continuum. *Operant Subjectivity: The International Journal of Q Methodology*, 34(3), 172–191.
- Risdon, A., Eccleston, C., Crombez, G., & McCracken, L. (2003). How can we learn to live with pain? A Q-methodological analysis of the diverse understandings of acceptance of chronic pain. *Social Science & Medicine*, 56(2), 375-386. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-9536\(02\)00043-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-9536(02)00043-6)
- Rogers, E. M., Singhal, A., & Quinlan, M. M. (2014). Diffusion of innovations. In *An integrated approach to communication theory and research* (pp. 432-448). Routledge.

Van Exel, J., & De Graaf, G. (2005). Q methodology: A sneak preview. *Social Sciences*, 2, 1–30.

Watts, S., & Stenner, P. (2007). Q methodology: The inverted factor technique. *The Irish Journal of Psychology*, 28(1-2), 63-76. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03033910.2007.10446249>

Watts, S., & Stenner, P. (2012). *Doing Q methodological research: Theory, method & interpretation*. London: Sage.

Webler, T., Tuler, S., Shockey, I., Stern, P., & Beattie, R. (2003). Participation by local governmental officials in watershed management planning. *Society and Natural Resources*, 16(2), 105–121.

Zagata, L. (2010). How organic farmers view their own practice: results from the Czech Republic. *Agriculture and Human Values*, 27, 277-290. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10460-009-9230-9>